

DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN INVERSES OF CONSECUTIVE INTEGERS MODULO P

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Abstract

Let $p > 2$ be a prime number. For each integer $0 < n < p$, define $\bar{n}$ by the congruence $n\bar{n} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ with $0 < \bar{n} < p$. We are led to study the distribution behavior of $\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}$ in order to prove the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n=1}^{p-2} |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}| = \frac{1}{3}p^2 + O(p^{3/2} \log^3 p).$$

1. Introduction

For any prime p and any integer $0 < n < p$, there is one and only one $\bar{n}$ with $0 < \bar{n} < p$ satisfying $n\bar{n} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. We are interested in how the inverses $\bar{n}$ fluctuate as n runs from 1 to $p-1$. In particular, we look at the sum

$$S_p = \sum_{n=1}^{p-2} |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}| \tag{1}$$

For any integer k , one can easily show that there are at most 2 solutions to the congruence equation $\bar{n} - \overline{n+1} \equiv k \pmod{p}$. From this, we have

$$\frac{1}{8}p^2 - \frac{1}{2}p \leq \sum_{n=1}^{[p/4]} 4k \leq S_p \leq \sum_{n=p-[p/4]-2}^{p-2} 4k \leq \frac{7}{8}p^2 + \frac{7}{2}p$$

where $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer $\leq x$. So, S_p has order p^2 and the natural question is whether $\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} S_p/p^2$ exists. To this, we have the following.

Theorem 1. For any prime $p > 2$,

$$S_p = \sum_{n=1}^{p-2} |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}| = \frac{1}{3}p^2 + O(p^{3/2} \log^3 p).$$

Hence, on average, the difference between inverses of consecutive integers, $|\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}|$, is about $p/3$. More generally, we have the following result.

Theorem 2. For any prime $p > 2$ and $\lambda > 0$,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{p-2} |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}|^\lambda = \frac{2}{(\lambda+1)(\lambda+2)} p^{\lambda+1} + O(p^{\lambda+1/2} \log^3 p).$$

To prove Theorem 1 or 2, we are led to study

$$\begin{aligned} T_+(p, k) &= \#\{n : 0 < n < p, 0 < \bar{n} - \overline{n+1} \leq k\}, \\ T_-(p, k) &= \#\{n : 0 < n < p, -k \leq \bar{n} - \overline{n+1} < 0\}, \text{ and} \\ T(p, k) &= T_+(p, k) + T_-(p, k) = \#\{n : 0 < n < p, 0 < |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}| \leq k\} \end{aligned}$$

for integer $0 < k < p$. We have

Theorem 3. For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p$,

$$T_\pm(p, k) = k - \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p).$$

Our method of proof is motivated by Professor W.P. Zhang's paper [5] involving Kloosterman sums and trigonometric sums. The proofs of Theorems 1, 2 and 3 extend to pairs $\bar{n}$ and $\overline{n+l}$ for fixed integer $l \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ with slight modifications.

2. Exponential and Kloosterman sums

First, we start with some notation. Letting $e(y) = e^{2\pi iy}$, we denote the Kloosterman sum

$$S(m, n; q) := \sum_{\substack{d \pmod{q} \\ (d, q) = 1}} e\left(\frac{md + n\bar{d}}{q}\right).$$

Lemma 1. Let p be a prime number. For any integer a and $b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$,

$$\sum'_{x=1}^p e\left(\frac{ax+b}{x(x\pm 1)p}\right) \ll p^{1/2}$$

where $\sum'$ is over all $x \pmod{p}$ except the roots of $x(x \pm 1)$ in F_p .

Proof. It follows from the Bombieri-Weil bound [1] for exponential sums in the form by Moreno and Moreno [4, Theorem 2] provided that $\frac{ax+b}{x(x\pm 1)}$ is not of the form $h(x)^p - h(x)$ with $h(x) \in \overline{F}_p$, where $\overline{F}_p$ is the algebraic closure of F_p . This is true in our situation. For otherwise, say

$$\frac{ax+b}{x(x\pm 1)} = \left(\frac{F(x)}{G(x)}\right)^p - \frac{F(x)}{G(x)}$$

with $F(x)$ and $G(x)$ polynomials over $\overline{F}_p$ such that $(F(x), G(x)) = 1$. Then

$$(ax+b)G(x)^p = x(x\pm 1)F(x)(F(x)^{p-1} - G(x)^{p-1}). \tag{2}$$

Since $F(x)$ and $G(x)$ are relatively prime, we have $G(x)^p | x(x\pm 1)$. This forces $G(x)$ to be a nonzero constant polynomial. Contradiction occurs if one compares the degrees in (2). $\square$

Lemma 2. *Let $p > 2$ be a prime number. For any integers r and s ,*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm n}{p}\right) S(r, n; p) \overline{S(s, n; p)} \ll p^{3/2}. \tag{3}$$

Here $\overline{S(s, n; p)}$ stands for the complex conjugate of $S(s, n; p)$.

Proof.

1. $r \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Then $S(r, n; p) = -1$ for $1 \leq n \leq p-1$. So, the left side of (3) is

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm n}{p}\right) \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-sd - n\bar{d}}{p}\right) \\ &= \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-sd}{p}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n(\bar{d} \mp 1)}{p}\right) \ll \sum_{\substack{d=1 \\ \bar{d} \neq \pm 1(p)}}^{p-1} 1 + p \ll p. \end{aligned}$$

2. $s \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Similar to case 1.

3. $r \not\equiv s \pmod{p}$ and $(r, p) = 1 = (s, p)$. The left hand side of (3)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm n}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{ra + n\bar{a}}{p}\right) \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-sb - n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\ &= \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{ra - sb}{p}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{(\bar{a} - \bar{b} \pm 1)n}{p}\right) \\ &= \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{r\bar{c} - s\bar{d}}{p}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{(c - d \pm 1)n}{p}\right) \\ &= (p-1) \sum'_{d=1} e\left(\frac{r\bar{d} \mp 1 - s\bar{d}}{p}\right) - \sum_{\substack{c=1 \\ c \neq d \mp 1}}^{p-1} \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{r\bar{c} - s\bar{d}}{p}\right) \\ &= p \sum'_{d=1} e\left(\frac{r\bar{d} \mp 1 - s\bar{d}}{p}\right) - \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{r\bar{c}}{p}\right) \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-s\bar{d}}{p}\right) \\ &= p \sum'_{d=1} e\left(\frac{[(r-s)d \pm s]\bar{d}(d \mp 1)}{p}\right) - 1 \ll p\sqrt{p} \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 1. Here $\sum'$ means summation over all d with $(d, p) = 1 = (d \mp 1, p)$. Note: The first sum in the second last line is a special case of Cobeli and Zaharescu [2, Lemma 1] or Cobeli, Gonek and Zaharescu [3, Lemma 1].

4. $r \equiv s \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Similar to case 3. □

3. Theorem 3 when $0 < k < p/2$

Now, we try to express $T_{\pm}(p, k)$ as exponential sums similar to [5].

Lemma 3. For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p/2$,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\pm}(p, k) &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \left[\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We shall only prove the formula for $T_+(p, k)$; the proof for $T_-(p, k)$ is similar. Observe that $T_+(p, k) = \#\{a : 0 < a - b \leq k, \bar{b} - \bar{a} = 1\}$. Thus, as

$$\sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{nr}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} p, & p \mid r; \\ 0, & p \nmid r, \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_+(p, k) &= \sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a-b=t, \bar{b}-\bar{a}=1}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} 1 \\
 &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p \sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a>b}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{m(a-b-t)}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{n(\bar{b}-\bar{a}-1)}{p}\right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{-mt}{p}\right) \left[\sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a>b}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{ma-n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{-mb+n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{b=p-k+1 \\ a>b}}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{ma-n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{-mb+n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \right] \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that we do not need the condition $\bar{b} > \bar{a}$ because $-p+2 \leq \bar{b}-\bar{a} \leq p-2$ which does not allow $\bar{b}-\bar{a} = 1-p$ (the only alternative besides 1 may be counted). Now $t-p \leq k-p$. It is valid to drop the condition $a > b$ in both double sums within the brackets because $k-p < 1-(p-k) \leq a-b$ and $k-p < -k < (p-k+1)-(p-1) \leq a-b$ respectively (note: $k < p/2$ is used for the second chain of inequalities). Hence, only $a-b = t$ is counted even without condition $a > b$ and we have the lemma. $\square$

Lemma 4. For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\
 &= kp(p-k) + O(p^{5/2} \log^2 p).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We separate the left hand side into three pieces according to: (i) $m = n = p$, (ii) $n = p$ and $1 \leq m \leq p-1$, (iii) $1 \leq m \leq p$ and $1 \leq n \leq p-1$. The left hand side of Lemma 4

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= kp(p-k) + O(p^2) + \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\pm ma}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb}{p}\right) \\
 &+ \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \tag{6} \\
 &= kp(p-k) + O(p^2) + S_1 + S_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$S_1 \leq \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \left| \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \right| \left| \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\mp mb}{p}\right) \right| \leq \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi m/p)|^2} \ll \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \frac{p^2}{m^2} \ll p^2 \tag{7}$$

by summing the geometric series and $\sin \pi x \geq 2x$ for $0 \leq x \leq 1/2$. By (4),

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{r=1}^p \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \sum_{c=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{r(b-c)}{p}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{r=1}^p \sum_{c=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{-cr}{p}\right) S(r \mp m, \pm n; p) \overline{S(\mp m, \pm n; p)}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by Lemma 2,

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 &\ll \frac{1}{p} \sum_{m=1}^p \left| \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \right| \sum_{r=1}^{p-1} \left| \sum_{c=1}^{p-k} e\left(\frac{-cr}{p}\right) \right| p^{3/2} + \sum_{m=1}^p \left| \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \right| p^{3/2} \\ &\ll p^{1/2} k \sum_{r=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi r/p)|} + p^{1/2} \left[\sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi m/p)|} \right]^2 + p^{3/2} k \\ &+ p^{3/2} \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi m/p)|} \ll p^{1/2} \left[\sum_{m=1}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \frac{p}{m} \right]^2 + p^{3/2} \sum_{m=1}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \frac{p}{m} \ll p^{5/2} \log^2 p. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Combining (6), (7) and (8), we have the lemma. □

Lemma 5. For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p/2$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}pk^2 + O(p^{5/2} \log^3 p). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Similar to Lemma 4, we split the left hand side into three pieces which

$$\begin{aligned} &= k^3 + O(p^2) + \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb}{p}\right) \\ &+ \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\ &= k^3 + O(p^2) + S_1 + S_2. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Replacing a by $p - a$ and b by $p - b$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1 &= \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{k-1} \sum_{b=1}^{k-1} e\left(\frac{\mp ma}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\pm mb}{p}\right) \\
 &= \sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{a=1}^{k-1} \sum_{b=1}^{k-1} \sum_{m=1}^p e\left(\frac{\pm m(b-a-t)}{p}\right) - k^3 + O(k^2) \\
 &= p \sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{a=1}^{k-1} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b-a=t}}^{k-1} 1 - k^3 + O(k^2) = \frac{1}{2}pk^2 - k^3 + O(pk)
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

because we may count $b - a = t$ or $b - a = t - p$ but the second case is not possible as $t - p \leq k - p < -k + 2 \leq b - a$. Here $k < p/2$ is crucial.

Applying (4) twice,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{a=p-k+1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{r=1}^p \sum_{s=1}^p \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{c=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{r(a-c)}{p}\right) \sum_{d=p-k+1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{s(b-d)}{p}\right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{r=1}^p \sum_{s=1}^p K(r)K(s)S(s \mp m, \pm n; p)\overline{S(\mp m - r, \pm n; p)}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $K(x) = \sum_{n=p-k+1}^{p-1} e(-nx/p)$. Rearranging the sums and applying Lemma 2,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_2 &= \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{mt}{p}\right) \sum_{r=1}^p \sum_{s=1}^p K(r)K(s) \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) S(s \mp m, \pm n; p)\overline{S(\mp m - r, \pm n; p)} \\
 &\ll \frac{1}{p^{1/2}} \sum_{m=1}^p \left| \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{mt}{p}\right) \right| \sum_{r=1}^p |K(r)| \sum_{s=1}^p |K(s)| \\
 &\ll \frac{1}{p^{1/2}} \left[k + \sum_{m=1}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi m/p)|} \right]^3 \ll \frac{1}{p^{1/2}} (k + p \log p)^3 \ll p^{5/2} \log^3 p.
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Combining (9), (10) and (11), we have the lemma. □

To prove Theorem 3 when $0 < k < p/2$, apply Lemma 4 and 5 to Lemma 3 and get

$$T_{\pm}(p, k) = \frac{1}{p^2} \left[kp(p - k) + \frac{1}{2}pk^2 + O(p^{5/2} \log^3 p) \right] = k - \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p)$$

which gives Theorem 3 in that range of k .

4. Theorem 3 when $p/2 < k < p$

Before proceeding, let us introduce some notation.

$$\begin{aligned} U_+(p, k) &= \#\{n : 0 < n < p, p - k \leq \overline{n - n + 1} < p\}, \\ U_-(p, k) &= \#\{n : 0 < n < p, -p < \overline{n - n + 1} \leq -p + k\}, \\ V_+(p, k) &= \#\{n; 0 < n < p, \overline{n - n + 1} \equiv t \pmod{p} \text{ for } 1 \leq t \leq k\}, \\ V_-(p, k) &= \#\{n; 0 < n < p, \overline{n - n + 1} \equiv -t \pmod{p} \text{ for } 1 \leq t \leq k\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then one can easily see that

$$V_+(p, k) = T_+(p, k) + U_-(p, k) \text{ and } V_-(p, k) = T_-(p, k) + U_+(p, k). \tag{12}$$

Lemma 6. *For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p$,*

$$V_{\pm}(p, k) = \frac{1}{p^2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right).$$

Proof. Use (4). Note: it is easier than Lemma 3 because one does not need to worry about $a > b$ or $a < b$. □

Lemma 7. *For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 < k < p$,*

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^p e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \\ &= kp^2 + O(p^{5/2} \log p) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Similar to Lemma 4, we split the left hand side into three pieces which

$$\begin{aligned} &= kp^2 + O(p^2) + \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb}{p}\right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{\pm ma \mp n\bar{a}}{p}\right) e\left(\frac{\mp mb \pm n\bar{b}}{p}\right) \tag{13} \\ &= kp^2 + O(p^2) + S_1 + S_2. \end{aligned}$$

By (4),

$$S_1 \leq \sum_{m=1}^{p-1} \sum_{t=1}^k 1 \ll p^2. \tag{14}$$

After rearranging summations,

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 &= \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{-n}{p}\right) S(\mp m, \pm n; p) \overline{S(\mp m, \pm n; p)} \\ &\ll p^{3/2} \sum_{m=1}^p \left| \sum_{t=1}^k e\left(\frac{\mp mt}{p}\right) \right| \\ &\ll p^{3/2} \left[k + \sum_{m=1}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi m/p)|} \right] \ll p^{3/2}(k + p \log p) \ll p^{5/2} \log p \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

by Lemma 2, summing the geometric series and $\sin(\pi x) \geq 2x$. We have the lemma by (13), (14) and (15). $\square$

Lemma 8. *For any prime $p > 2$ and any integer $0 \leq k < p/2$,*

$$U_{\pm}(p, k) = \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p).$$

Proof. First note that when $k = 0$, $U_{\pm}(p, k) = 0$. Now assume $k > 0$. From (12), $U_{\pm}(p, k) = V_{\mp}(p, k) - T_{\mp}(p, k)$. Thus, by Lemma 6, 7 and Theorem 3 in the range $0 < k < p/2$,

$$U_{\pm}(p, k) = k + O(p^{1/2} \log p) - \left(k - \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p) \right)$$

which gives the lemma. $\square$

To prove Theorem 3 when $p/2 < k < p$, observe that $0 \leq p - k - 1 < p/2$ and

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\pm}(p, k) &= T_{\pm}\left(p, \frac{p-1}{2}\right) + \left[U_{\pm}\left(p, \frac{p-1}{2}\right) - U_{\pm}(p, p-k-1) \right] \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} - \frac{(\frac{p-1}{2})^2}{2p} + \left[\frac{(\frac{p-1}{2})^2}{2p} - \frac{(p-k-1)^2}{2p} \right] + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p) \\ &= \frac{p}{2} - \frac{p^2 - 2pk + k^2}{2p} + O(1) + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p) \\ &= k - \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p) \end{aligned}$$

by Theorem 3 in the range $0 < k < p/2$ and Lemma 8.

5. Proof of Theorems 1 and 2

By Theorem 3, $T(p, k) = 2k - k^2/p + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p)$ for integer $0 < k < p$. More generally,

$$T(p, u) = \#\{n : 0 < |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}| \leq u\} = 2u - \frac{u^2}{p} + O(p^{1/2} \log^3 p) \tag{16}$$

for any real number $0 \leq u \leq p$. Using the Riemann-Stieltjes integral, integration by parts, and (16),

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{p-2} |\bar{n} - \overline{n+1}|^\lambda &= \int_0^p u^\lambda dT(p, u) = T(p, p)p^\lambda - \lambda \int_0^p u^{\lambda-1} T(p, u) du \\ &= p^{\lambda+1} + O(p^\lambda) - \lambda \int_0^p 2u^\lambda - \frac{u^{\lambda+1}}{p} + O(u^{\lambda-1} p^{1/2} \log^3 p) du \\ &= p^{\lambda+1} - \left[\frac{2\lambda}{\lambda+1} p^{\lambda+1} - \frac{\lambda}{\lambda+2} p^{\lambda+1} \right] + O(p^{\lambda+1/2} \log^3 p) \\ &= \frac{2}{(\lambda+1)(\lambda+2)} p^{\lambda+1} + O(p^{\lambda+1/2} \log^3 p) \end{aligned}$$

which gives Theorem 2 and hence Theorem 1.

Numerical calculations (by a C++ program) suggest that the error term in Theorem 3 is probably best possible except for the extra logarithms.

Let $m_p^\pm = \max_{1 \leq k < p} |T_\pm(p, k) - (k - \frac{k^2}{2p})|$.

p	101	103	107	109	113	127	131	137
$m_p^+/\sqrt{p}$	0.4951	0.6103	0.9794	0.7504	0.4595	0.9122	0.6133	0.6401
$m_p^-/\sqrt{p}$	0.5951	0.7098	0.6993	0.4956	0.4812	0.7976	0.9067	0.5416
p	5501	5503	5507	5519	5521	5527	5531	5557
$m_p^+/\sqrt{p}$	0.5786	0.6384	0.7021	0.6350	1.1337	0.4528	0.6928	0.7150
$m_p^-/\sqrt{p}$	0.5945	0.6532	0.7342	0.5888	1.0775	0.4621	0.7291	0.7530
p	12301	12323	12329	12343	12347	12373	12377	12379
$m_p^+/\sqrt{p}$	0.5249	0.6978	0.8166	1.0416	1.1251	0.6540	0.8172	0.6914
$m_p^-/\sqrt{p}$	0.5521	0.6745	0.8101	1.0346	1.1069	0.6789	0.8144	0.6778
p	60013	60017	60029	60037	60041	60077	60083	60089
$m_p^+/\sqrt{p}$	0.5172	0.7776	0.5806	0.8265	0.8441	0.9457	0.4469	0.5922
$m_p^-/\sqrt{p}$	0.5312	0.7789	0.5792	0.8411	0.8489	0.9514	0.4373	0.5897

We conclude with the following

Conjecture 1.

$$m_p^\pm \ll p^{1/2} \quad \text{and} \quad m_p^+ - m_p^- = o(p^{1/2}).$$

Note: After finishing this paper, we came across Cobeli and Zaharescu [2], and found that it is far more general and would give

$$T_\pm(p, k) = k - \frac{k^2}{2p} + O(p^{5/6} \log^{2/3} p).$$

Hence their method gives our results except for a bigger error term.

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